

A New Anthraquinone from the Pods of *Cassia grandis* Linn.

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Cassia grandis Linn. belongs to the Caesalpinaceae (sub-family : Leguminosae) and abundantly present in northern India. It has been used for acidic, mucilaginous and cathartic properties¹. Pulp from the pods of this plant is a powerful laxative².

The air-dried powdered pods of *C. grandis* furnished a compound $C_{17}H_{14}O_8$, m.p. 214–15° (yellow needles) which gave colour reactions³ and uv absorption^{4,5} characteristic of hydroxyanthraquinone. 2-Methyl anthracene as the Zn-dust distillation product indicated that the compound may have 2-methylanthraquinone skeleton. On acetylation it gave tetraacetate showing the presence of four hydroxyl groups. Reddish purple colour with methanolic magnesium acetate showed the presence of chelated (α -OH) hydroxyl group⁶. Solubility of the compound in 5% aqueous sodium carbonate, a peak at ν_{\max} 3 440 cm^{-1} and λ_{\max} 378 nm^4 showed the presence of at least one β -hydroxyl group. Ir bands at 2 916 and 2 880 cm^{-1} indicated the presence of methoxyl and C-methyl groups respectively. It contains two methoxyl groups⁸. The compound got demethylated with 80% sulphuric acid indicating that at least one methoxyl group must be at α -position to the carbonyl group⁹. A sharp and strong peak at 1605 cm^{-1} suggested that both the carbonyl groups were chelated with hydroxyl group⁷. The presence of λ_{\max} 487 nm^4 and ν_{\max} at 1 605 cm^{-1} showed that the compound has only three α -hydroxyl groups.

The ir peak at 1 605 cm^{-1} also showed the presence of 1,4,5-trihydroxy system¹⁰. ¹H nmr spectra of the compound showed signals corresponding to one C-methyl (δ 2.32 : 3H, s, C-2), two methoxyl (δ 3.98 : 3H, s, C-7; 4.06 : 3H, s, C-8) groups, one aromatic proton (δ 6.85 : 1H, d, J 2.5 Hz, H-6) and four hydroxyl (δ 12.03: 1H, s, C-3; 12.88: 3H, s, C-1, C-4, C-5) groups. Thus the anthraquinone was identified as 1,3,4,5-tetrahydroxy-7,8-dimethoxy-2-methylanthraquinone. This assignment was also confirmed by standard colour reactions^{6,11}.

The air dried powdered material of pods of *C. grandis* was extracted in a soxhlet extractor using petroleum ether, benzene and ethyl acetate in succession. A yellow coloured compound was isolated from ethyl acetate extract by column chromatography using benzene-ethyl acetate (2 : 8, v/v) as eluant and silica gel G as absorbent. The compound was crystallised as yellow needles from petroleum ether (b.p. 60–80°)-ethyl acetate mixture (1 : 1, v/v), $C_{17}H_{14}O_8$; m.p. 214–15° (Found : C, 58.36; H, 4.29 $C_{17}H_{14}O_8$ calcd. for : C, 58.90; H, 4.04%); acetate (Ac_2O/Py), m.p. 205° (Found:acetyl, 42.45. $C_{17}H_{10}O_4$ - ($OCOCH_3$)₄ calcd. for:42.02%); methyl ether (Me_2SO_4/K_2CO_3), m.p. 197° (Found : methoxy, 46.82. $C_{15}H_4O_2$ - (OCH_3)₆ calcd. for : 46.20%); (Found : methoxy in the compound : 18.12. $C_{15}H_8O_6(OCH_3)_2$ calcd. for : 17.90%); λ_{\max} (EtOH) 274, 378, 487 nm; ν_{\max} (KBr) 3 440, 2 916, 2 880, 1 669, 1 605,

1 180, 735–725 cm^{-1} ; ^1H nmr δ (CDCl_3 ; 100 MHz) 2.32 (3H, s, CH_3), 3.98 (3H, s, OCH_3), 4.06 (3H, s, OCH_3), 6.85 (1H, d, J 2.5 Hz, H-6), 12.03 (1H, s, OH) and 12.88 (3H, s, 3 \times OH).

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